

Content Based Retrieval for Distributed Data Trading Platforms

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Abstract—Enabling content-based search in federated data marketplaces, where assets remain distributed and secure, is a significant challenge. This paper introduces a two-stage “retrieve, then re-rank” solution. We present a comparative analysis of Approximate Nearest Neighbor (ANN) and Learning to Rank (LTR) methods, justifying our selection of Locality-Sensitive Hashing (LSH) for retrieval and a weak supervision strategy for re-ranking. Finally, we detail the architecture of the PISTIS distributed query engine, a novel system that implements this approach to provide effective, policy-aware search across federated data sources.

Index Terms—Distributed Systems, Data Trading Platforms, Information Retrieval, LSH, Re-Ranking.

I. INTRODUCTION

The proliferation of data as a tradable asset has led to the emergence of sophisticated data marketplaces and trading platforms. Within these ecosystems, effective data discovery remains a significant challenge, moving beyond simple keyword searches to address the complex needs of users seeking specific data content. A critical dichotomy exists between metadata-based retrieval, which queries dataset descriptions and content-based retrieval, which enables searching based on the similarity of the data itself. Addressing this requires a robust information retrieval architecture capable of handling diverse, high-dimensional data in dynamic environments where datasets are frequently created, updated and deleted.

The system that is discussed in this paper is developed in the context of the PISTIS [1] data trading platform, a European initiative that provides a federated data sharing, trading and monetization platform for the secure, trusted and controlled exchange of industrial data assets. A core principle of the PISTIS platform is that data assets remain under the control of the owner at all times, with only metadata being exposed to orchestrate the platform’s services. This approach creates a trustworthy environment where the value of data can be unlocked in a fair and transparent manner but comes with the challenge of requiring distributed data querying and discovery that adheres to each individual organization’s data usage and visibility policies.

This paper addresses the challenge of data discovery in such platforms by analyzing the components of a two-stage paradigm: first retrieve, then re-rank. Our key contributions are twofold. First, we provide a comprehensive comparative

evaluation of state-of-the-art indexing and re-ranking techniques, analyzing their suitability for the unique constraints of the dataset trading platform environment. We examine the trade-offs between different families of Approximate Nearest Neighbor (ANN) search and Learning to Rank (LTR) methodologies. Second, we present the architecture and functionalities of the PISTIS distributed query module, a novel system that implements these principles to enable advanced content-based search capabilities within distributed data trading platforms.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section II provides a literature review and taxonomy, covering indexing techniques for high-dimensional data in Subsection II-A and re-ranking techniques in information retrieval systems in Subsection II-B. Section III evaluates these techniques specifically within the context of data management and trading platforms. Section IV details the PISTIS distributed query solution, including the selection of methods and its system architecture. Finally, Section V concludes the paper with a summary of our findings.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND TAXONOMY

A. Indexing Techniques for High-Dimensional and Multi-modal Data

Efficient information retrieval from large-scale datasets is fundamental to modern data systems. A foundational method for text is the inverted index, a data structure that maps terms to the documents they appear in, enabling rapid keyword searches. While indispensable for search engines, it is limited to discrete, tokenizable data and is ill-suited for the continuous, high-dimensional vectors representing modern data like image embeddings or genomic sequences.

Retrieval in these vector spaces is framed as a Nearest Neighbor (NN) search, which aims to find the data points closest to a query vector. However, performing an exact NN search by exhaustively comparing a query with every point is computationally prohibitive due to the “curse of dimensionality”. To make NN search tractable, Approximate Nearest Neighbor (ANN) search trades perfect accuracy for significant speed gains by retrieving points that are probably the nearest neighbors. The ANN landscape is dominated by three main families of techniques: hashing, quantization, and graph-based methods.

1) *Hashing-Based Methods*: Locality-Sensitive Hashing (LSH) is a pioneering family of algorithms for ANN search. Its core principle is that specialized hash functions should make similar items more likely to collide into the same bucket, probabilistically reducing the search space. LSH developed from classic schemes to modern frameworks that address earlier limitations.

The foundational LSH techniques created compact "fingerprints" of data to preserve a specific similarity measure.

MinHash: Introduced by Broder [2], MinHash estimates the Jaccard similarity between two sets (e.g., shingles of a document). Instead of slow permutations, it uses multiple hash functions to create a compact signature vector for each set. The fraction of matching values in two signatures rapidly approximates their Jaccard similarity.

SimHash: Developed by Charikar et al. [3], SimHash addresses cosine similarity for weighted feature vectors. It generates a compact b-bit fingerprint where the Hamming distance between two fingerprints approximates the angle between the original vectors. This makes it highly effective for near-duplicate detection in large corpora, as famously used by Google.

Classic LSH schemes often require many hash tables for high recall, leading to large memory footprints and numerous false positives. Modern LSH frameworks address these issues with more sophisticated indexing.

PM-LSH: Proposed by Zheng et al. [4], this framework replaces flat hash tables with a PM-tree. This tree partitions data based on reference points, allowing the search to quickly prune branches that cannot contain the neighbor. This hierarchical approach reduces candidate checks, improving both speed and accuracy.

DB-LSH: The Database-inspired LSH scheme from Ouyang et al. [5] uses multi-dimensional indexes (like B⁺-trees) to organize projected data. It dynamically constructs query-specific buckets via efficient window queries on these indexes. This "just-in-time" creation avoids storing numerous hash tables, yielding a smaller, higher-quality candidate set and a provably lower query cost.

2) *Quantization-Based Methods*: Vector quantization techniques reduce the memory footprint of high-dimensional vectors by trading exactness for memory savings and faster approximate distance calculations.

Product Quantization (PQ): Introduced by Jégou et al. [6], PQ is a landmark vector compression technique. It decomposes a high-dimensional vector space into a Cartesian product of lower-dimensional subspaces and quantizes each independently. This enables efficient distance calculations, such as Asymmetric Distance Computation (ADC), without decompressing the vectors, often using pre-calculated lookup tables to accelerate queries. Variants like IVFPQ, popularized by the FAISS library [7], combine PQ with an inverted file system for a coarse-to-fine search.

3) *Graph-Based Methods*: Graph-based methods are the current state-of-the-art for many ANN workloads, offering su-

perior accuracy-speed trade-offs. They construct a graph where data points are nodes and edges connect close neighbors.

Hierarchical Navigable Small World (HNSW): Proposed by Malkov et al. [8], HNSW builds a multi-layer, hierarchical graph. Upper layers are sparse for coarse traversal, while the bottom layer contains all data for fine-grained accuracy. A search starts at the top layer, greedily navigating to find an entry point for the layer below, progressively refining the result. A heuristic for selecting diverse neighbors during construction enhances connectivity and helps avoid local minima. This layered approach provides high recall with quasi-logarithmic time complexity, making HNSW a popular choice for modern vector search.

B. *Re-Ranking techniques in information retrieval systems*

Re-ranking is a critical second stage in information retrieval systems. It refines an initial candidate list, generated by a fast retrieval model, to produce a more relevant final ranking. This two-stage process balances computational efficiency with high-quality results. Methodologies are broadly categorized as query-centric, user-centric, document-centric, and machine-learned.

1) *Query and User-Centric Refinements*: These techniques aim to better understand user intent. Methods like Query Expansion, as seen in the classic Rocchio algorithm [9], add related terms to the original query. User feedback is also crucial, whether explicit (direct labels) or **implicit** (inferred from behaviors like clicks and dwell time) [10]. This interaction data helps build long-term user preference models to personalize rankings.

2) *Document-Centric and Ensemble Approaches*: This strategy re-evaluates documents using richer features than are feasible during initial retrieval. Document Re-Scoring recalculates relevance based on deeper properties like freshness or source authority. Furthermore, Ensemble Methods create a more robust final list by combining rankings from multiple, diverse models. These lists can be merged with techniques like Reciprocal Rank Fusion (RRF), which rewards documents that consistently rank high across different models [11].

3) *Learning to Rank (LTR)*: The most sophisticated and widely adopted re-ranking approach is Learning to Rank (LTR). This data-driven paradigm treats ranking as a supervised machine learning problem, training models on query-document data annotated with relevance labels. The field of LTR is generally categorized into three approaches [12]:

- 1) **Pointwise**: Each document is assigned an individual relevance score, and the final list is sorted by these scores.
- 2) **Pairwise**: The model learns to predict which of two documents is more relevant to a query. Models like RankNet use gradient descent on pairs of documents to optimize their ordering [13].
- 3) **Listwise**: The model attempts to directly optimize the quality of the entire ranked list. LambdaMART, a highly successful and widely used algorithm, is a prominent example of this approach [14].

TABLE I
COMPARATIVE OVERVIEW OF HIGH-DIMENSIONAL INDEXING TECHNIQUES

Technique Family	Core Principle	Key Innovation / Notable Works	Strengths & Weaknesses
Inverted Index	Maps discrete tokens to document lists.	Fast keyword-based retrieval.	(+) Extremely fast for keywords. (-) Not applicable to dense vector data.
Classic LSH	Similar items collide in the same hash bucket.	MinHash [2], SimHash [3]	(+) Sub-linear query time in theory. (-) High memory usage; often lower accuracy.
Modern LSH	Hierarchical or dynamic index structures replace flat hash tables.	PM-LSH [4], DB-LSH [5]	(+) Addresses classic LSH flaws. (-) More complex.
Quantization-Based	Compresses vectors by quantizing sub-vectors.	PQ [6], IVFADC (FAISS), ScaNN	(+) Massive memory reduction. (-) Lossy compression can impact accuracy.
Graph-Based	Search is a guided traversal on a graph of neighbors.	HNSW [8]	(+) State-of-the-art accuracy-speed trade-off. (-) High memory usage; complex build process.

III. EVALUATION WITHIN DATA MANAGEMENT AND TRADING PLATFORMS

A. Indexing techniques

For a platform dedicated to the trading of diverse datasets, the central challenge is enabling users to discover valuable assets within a vast, heterogeneous catalog. While keyword search on metadata is a start, the true innovation lies in content-based discovery. This analysis compares the primary indexing paradigms, highlighting why Locality-Sensitive Hashing (LSH) provides a powerful, scalable and uniquely versatile foundation for this task.

1) *Metadata vs. Content*: Any robust discovery system must handle two distinct query types: searching by description and searching by example. The most effective architecture uses specialized tools for each. The inverted index remains the undisputed champion for metadata search. It is perfectly suited for indexing dataset descriptions, user tags and data dictionaries, allowing for extremely fast, memory-efficient keyword queries [15]. However, it is fundamentally incapable of understanding content similarity.

To move beyond a simple "card catalog", a platform needs to enable content-based discovery. This is where vector search techniques, particularly LSH, become transformative. By operating on vector embeddings of the data itself, LSH unlocks the platform's most valuable feature: query-by-example. A user can upload a sample—an image, a genomic sequence, a data record—and find entire datasets containing similar content, a level of discoverability an inverted index cannot provide.

2) *Comparison of Content-Based Search Techniques*: While several methods for content-based search exist, they offer different trade-offs in terms of versatility, performance and complexity.

The fundamental strength of Locality-Sensitive Hashing (LSH) lies in its remarkable versatility and architectural simplicity. It is an adaptable framework that supports various data types and similarity measures through specialized hash families: MinHash for set-based data [2], SimHash for text embeddings [3] and LSH based on *p-stable distributions* for numerical vectors [16]. This makes it a "Swiss Army knife" for a marketplace with heterogeneous data.

Crucially, most LSH families do not require a costly, data-dependent training phase, simplifying the indexing pipeline

and allowing new datasets to be added on the fly without rebuilding the entire structure. Unlike quantization methods that require a computationally expensive training phase to learn codebooks from the data, LSH hash functions are data-independent. They are fixed beforehand based on the desired similarity metric. This means that the indexing pipeline is simplified as the complex and slow training step is removed and new datasets can be added without needing to rebuild the entire structure, a crucial feature for a dynamic marketplace.

Of course, the classic LSH framework is not without its challenges. To achieve high recall, it can require a large number of hash tables, leading to a significant memory footprint, which was a primary criticism [17]. Recognizing this, modern advancements within the LSH family have been developed specifically to mitigate these issues. For instance, PM-LSH [4] uses a hierarchical PM-tree for more efficient searching, while DB-LSH [5] borrows concepts from database indexing to create dynamic, query-specific buckets. These modern variants make the LSH family a much stronger contender in today's high-performance landscape.

When considering alternatives, Quantization-based methods, like the Product Quantization (PQ) used in FAISS [6], offer superior memory compression but at the cost of a mandatory training phase to create their codebooks, adding complexity to the indexing pipeline. Graph-based indexes like HNSW [8], while providing state-of-the-art query speed and accuracy, sacrifice the architectural simplicity and parallelizability of LSH. Their graph structures are memory-intensive and complex to build and maintain, especially in dynamic environments. Thus, these alternatives often trade LSH's training-free nature and scalability for specific performance gains.

B. Re-Ranking techniques

The re-ranking stage serves to refine the candidate set generated by an initial retrieval phase, such as Locality-Sensitive Hashing, by applying more computationally intensive but accurate models. Within a dataset marketplace, this stage is critical for ordering candidate datasets based on a nuanced understanding of relevance. LTR provides a data-driven framework for this task by treating ranking as a supervised machine learning problem. The three main LTR paradigms—pointwise, pairwise and listwise—offer distinct

trade-offs between implementation complexity, computational cost and the theoretical fidelity of the optimization objective.

The pointwise approach decomposes the ranking problem into a standard regression or classification task over individual query-document pairs. It learns a function, $f(q, d) \rightarrow s$, that maps a given query q and dataset d to a numerical relevance score s . The primary merit of this approach lies in its simplicity and its direct compatibility with a vast array of well-established machine learning algorithms. A significant application in this context is the use of deep semantic models to compute a relevance score based on the interaction between a user’s query and the textual metadata of a dataset. However, the theoretical limitation of the pointwise approach is its assumption of instance independence.

Pairwise methods offer a more refined optimization objective by recasting the ranking problem as the task of learning relative preferences. Instead of predicting an absolute score, these methods learn to predict the probability that one document is more relevant than another for a given query. This formulation is particularly adept at learning to make trade-offs between the heterogeneous features that define a high-quality asset in a dataset marketplace. Despite its advantage, the pairwise objective remains a proxy for true listwise ranking quality, as it does not directly optimize metrics like Normalized Discounted Cumulated Gain (NDCG) that depend on the positions of documents in the list.

The listwise paradigm represents the current state-of-the-art in LTR, seeking to address the limitations of the aforementioned methods by treating the entire ranked list as the fundamental unit of optimization. Listwise algorithms are designed to directly optimize a loss function that serves as a surrogate for standard information retrieval evaluation metrics like NDCG. For a dataset marketplace, where user satisfaction and successful transactions are heavily influenced by the quality of the top-ranked results, the listwise approach is theoretically the most effective and has demonstrated superior performance in a wide array of applications. The primary trade-offs are increased model complexity and greater computational cost during the training phase.

IV. A DISTRIBUTED QUERY SOLUTION FOR PISTIS

A. *Methods selection*

The selection of an indexing methodology for a dynamic data repository like the PISTIS platform requires a careful evaluation of the trade-offs between query performance, memory overhead and, critically, maintenance costs under high data churn. In an environment characterized by moderately-sized but heterogeneous and rapidly changing datasets, Locality-Sensitive Hashing (LSH) emerges as a particularly compelling solution. Its architectural properties offer a robust balance of flexibility and operational simplicity that aligns well with the specific constraints of PISTIS.

A primary advantage of the LSH framework is its inherent flexibility and data-type agnosticism. The PISTIS platform, designed to manage a diverse catalog of datasets, must accommodate multiple data modalities, and LSH’s adaptability

ensures that a single, coherent indexing strategy can be applied across the platform’s varied assets. However, the most decisive factor favoring LSH for PISTIS is its superior handling of dynamic data collections where creation, update, and deletion operations are frequent.

Alternative high-performance indexing families exhibit significant maintenance overhead in such scenarios. For instance, quantization-based methods depend on a data-dependent training phase to generate their codebooks. In a high-churn environment, the underlying data distribution can shift, causing these codebooks to become stale and degrading search quality over time, which in turn necessitates periodic, computationally expensive retraining that would introduce an operational bottleneck. Similarly, graph-based indexes like HNSW [8] build highly interconnected and optimized structures. While offering excellent query performance, this complexity poses challenges for dynamic maintenance, as node deletion is a non-trivial operation requiring careful relinking of edges to prevent the degradation of the graph’s navigable properties and overall search performance.

In contrast, the LSH architecture is fundamentally simpler and more resilient to change. The indexing process—hashing each item independently—is stateless and highly parallelizable. Because the hash functions are data-independent, adding new items is a straightforward operation, and deleting items requires only their removal from the hash tables without affecting the index’s global structure. This ability to gracefully manage frequent updates without costly retraining or complex structural maintenance is a significant architectural advantage for the PISTIS Data Factory model.

Regarding the second major component of PISTIS Distributed Query engine, the primary challenge in designing the re-ranking stage for a dataset marketplace is the inherent “cold start” problem. This issue arises from the complete absence of historical user interaction data, which is the cornerstone of modern, supervised ranking models. Contemporary re-ranking systems based on Learning to Rank (LTR) are predicated on the availability of large-scale datasets containing implicit user feedback (e.g., clicks, downloads, purchases) or explicit relevance judgments. Without such data, a new platform such as PISTIS faces a critical problem: while the initial retrieval stage can identify a set of potentially relevant candidates, there is no empirical basis to determine the most relevant or valuable items within that set.

This challenge is compounded by the multi-faceted nature of relevance in a dataset marketplace. The value of a dataset is not determined by a single factor, but is rather a complex function of content match, data quality, completeness, provenance, freshness and usage rights. In a mature system, a machine learning model would learn the implicit weights and trade-offs between these different facets by observing which datasets successful users ultimately choose. In the absence of this feedback loop at launch, the system cannot learn these crucial relationships. Therefore, the initial implementation of the re-ranking module must rely on a *proxy for relevance* that is derived not from user behavior, but from the intrinsic,

observable properties of the datasets themselves. While a simple heuristic function is a viable starting point, modern machine learning techniques offer more sophisticated solutions to the cold start problem, primarily through transfer learning and weak supervision.

A common and self-contained strategy is to use the platform’s own domain knowledge to bootstrap a machine learning model. This falls under the paradigm of weak supervision, where models are trained using noisy or programmatic labels instead of hand-annotated ground truth [18]. This process begins by defining a set of heuristics based on intrinsic metadata, e.g. rules that assign higher scores to datasets with greater completeness, more recent update times, or more reputable providers.

The outputs of these heuristics are then used as pseudo-labels to train a more complex, non-linear model, such as a gradient boosting tree or a neural network [19]. This approach is conceptually a form of knowledge distillation [20]. The simple, interpretable heuristic acts as the “teacher”, and the machine learning model acts as the “student”. The benefit of this process is not that the student model discovers new, external truths about relevance; its performance is ultimately bounded by the quality of the teacher heuristic. Instead, the advantage lies in the student’s ability to learn a more powerful and generalized representation of the teacher’s knowledge. A non-linear model can capture complex feature interactions (e.g., “provider reputation is especially important for less fresh data”) and non-linear relationships that a simple weighted-sum heuristic cannot express. It effectively learns a smoother, more nuanced approximation of the domain expertise encoded in the initial rules, resulting in a more robust ranking function that can be deployed from day one. This weakly supervised model then serves as a powerful baseline, ready to be fine-tuned with real user feedback as the platform matures.

B. System Architecture

The Distributed Query Engine is designed as an extension to the Piveau Open Data catalogue [21]. Piveau is a comprehensive data management solution based on Semantic Web standards such as DCAT and RDF, providing robust capabilities for publishing and managing dataset metadata. While its search functionality is highly optimized for querying this rich, structured metadata, it does not natively support searching based on the raw content of the datasets themselves. The Distributed Query Engine directly addresses this limitation by introducing a content-based retrieval mechanism. It functions as a complementary service that allows users to perform query-by-example searches, thus discovering datasets based on the similarity of their actual data, not just their descriptions. This integration creates a holistic search experience, combining Piveau’s metadata-driven discovery with the engine’s content-based retrieval capabilities.

To achieve this, the engine is architected as a modular system decomposed into three core components: a central Distributed Query Service acting as an orchestrator, multiple instances of a Locality-Sensitive Hashing (LSH) Component

for candidate retrieval and a final ReRanker for result optimization. The overall architecture is depicted in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The PISTIS Distributed Query Engine Architecture.

Serving as the central control plane, the **Distributed Query Service** orchestrates the end-to-end search process. It is the primary entry point for user-initiated search requests. Upon receiving a query, the service dispatches it in parallel to the LSH components deployed in each distributed data nodes (also referred to as “Data Factory” within the PISTIS platform). Once the retrieval tasks are complete, the service aggregates the returned candidate sets, which consist of lists of unique dataset identifiers (UUIDs). Before further processing, this aggregated list is passed to an Identity and Access Management (IAM) service to perform authorization checks, filtering out datasets the user is not permitted to access. Subsequently, the service enriches the remaining candidates by retrieving their detailed metadata from the Data Catalogue. This final, filtered and enriched list is then passed to the ReRanker for scoring and sorting before being presented to the end-user.

The **LSH Component** functions as the core retrieval engine, with an independent instance deployed at each Data Factory. This component is responsible for indexing the datasets persisted in the local Data Storage. Its design is modular, comprising four distinct modules. The *Index Manager* is responsible for generating the LSH hashes that form the content-based signature of each dataset; this module is triggered automatically upon the insertion or update of a dataset, ensuring the index remains current. The generated signatures are persisted in the *Hashes Storage* module. The *Query Executor* module receives search requests from the central service and performs the Approximate Nearest Neighbor (ANN) search against the local index to retrieve the most relevant local datasets. Finally, a *Controller* module encapsulates the component’s logic and exposes a consistent API for interaction with other services within the ecosystem.

The final stage of the query pipeline is managed by the **ReRanker** component, which is responsible for fusing and re-ordering the aggregated list of candidates into a single, highly relevant result set. This component operates using machine learning models and is divided into two functional modules.

An offline *Training Module* is responsible for learning a ranking model based on a set of features, as discussed in our re-ranking methodology. The online *Inference Module* then uses this pre-trained model to predict a relevance score for each candidate dataset in the unified list, producing the final, accurately sorted results that are presented to the user.

At the end of the whole workflow, the user is presented with the relevant query results (datasets) that have been extracted from all the distributed data nodes (data factories), filtered based on the data usage and visibility policies of each organization that controls the data factories and, finally, ranked based on relevance. This gives, to the data trading platform users, easy access to distributed data assets without sacrificing security, usability and while keeping high retrieval relevance.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper we presented our approach to distributed query engines that operate within data trading platform environments such as the PISTIS distributed data trading platform. We presented a comparative evaluation of state-of-the-art indexing and re-ranking techniques, analyzing their suitability for the unique constraints of the data trading platform environments. We also presented the architecture and functionalities of the PISTIS distributed query module that implements those principles to enable advanced content-based search capabilities within such distributed data trading platforms. We showed how, through the systematic evaluation and clever usage of existing indexing and re-ranking techniques, such a distributed query engine can offer easy to use and relevant access to data assets within distributed data trading platforms, while adhering to the usage policies of each data owning organization within the platform.

With the PISTIS platform and the described query engine now deployed, our immediate focus shifts to comprehensive empirical validation and iterative refinement as we onboard datasets and users. Our future work will commence with extensive benchmarking of the live retrieval component, comparing our LSH-based approach against state-of-the-art alternatives like HNSW. Concurrently, we will formally evaluate the effectiveness of the implemented weak supervision strategy by measuring the uplift in ranking quality of the trained "student" model over the baseline "teacher" heuristic, thereby quantifying the value of this knowledge distillation approach. As the platform's user base grows and provides real interaction data, we will leverage this feedback to fine-tune the re-ranking model, transitioning from a weakly supervised to a fully supervised Learning to Rank paradigm. Finally, comprehensive end-to-end stress tests will be performed on the deployed infrastructure to assess its scalability and robustness as the number of participating data factories and the volume of datasets increase.

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